

INTRODUCTION

The Far Eastern Federal District is the largest in the Russian Federation. However, a wide range of socio-economic problems leads to depopulation and hinders implementation of government tasks. The Territories of Advanced Socio-economic Development (TASED or TAD) created in the Far Eastern Federal District can improve the socio-economic and agricultural sectors. The relevancelies in the fact that the TASED is a new tool for developing the Far Eastern Federal District; functioning of these territories raises certain questions.

In particular, the Russian Far East is facing economic backwardness, low population density, and insufficient infrastructure. Creating TASED is also associated with improving the quality of life of the local population, creating jobs, and increasing income levels. In addition, the Far East is strategically important to Russia in the context of relations with neighboring countries such as China, Japan, and Korea.

Thus, studying the effectiveness of the TASED in the Far Eastern Federal District is an essential step towards understanding the mechanisms of economic growth and social stability in this strategically important region of Russia. The study aims to conduct a comparative analysis of such effectiveness.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodological basis of the research is a systematic and comprehensive analysis and synthesis of the problem under consideration using economic and statistical methods, as well as a dialectical method involving the study of phenomena in dynamic development.

The theoretical basis of the research is two main groups of scientific papers: analyzing issues related to the organization and activities of the TASED throughout the Russian Federation and using the example of the Far Eastern Federal District. In addition, researchers are interested in creating a TASED as a means of ensuring food security and improving the agricultural sector.

Research information base: data from the Official website of the Corporation for the Development of the Far East and the Arctic, information and analytical material from the Analytical Department of the Office of the Federation Council of the Russian Federation.

The research materials also included articles in scientific journals on economics, regional development, and public administration (Regional Research of Russia, Studies on Russian Economic Development, Journal of the Economy of the Region, Scientific Research of the Faculty of Economics, etc.).

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. I. Treivish and T. V. Litvinenko clarify Eastern Russia's concept and borders and its position in the country and the world. The authors determined that Eastern Russia's strong socio-economic dispersion is due to continuing underdevelopment of the territory associated with harsh natural conditions, history, and geographical asymmetry of development. However, Eastern Russia is a vast resource, an ecological and ethnocultural reserve [1].

V. E. Seliverstov reveals the features of the so-called Eastern vector of Russia's spatial development as a new element of the country's spatial policy and an important area of its cross-border interactions. The author shows that its implementation is dominated by state support for Far Eastern investment projects and priority development territories. At the same time, Siberia and its regions are practically excluded from this strategic initiative [2].

N. G. Dzhurka examines possible development trajectories of the Far East which are shaped by the policy of creating preferences for economic activity in the region. The author analyzes various complementary schemes for stimulating economic activity in the Far East and evaluates the dependence of economic growth on the scale of government support [3].

P. A. Minakir describes proposals for a long-term policy for the region's development and the problems of forming a state regional policy in relation to the Far Eastern Economic Region and Transbaikalia. The authors provide suggestions on emergency measures to be implemented in the region itself to stabilize the socio-economic situation and urge development based on market relations and cooperation with the countries of the Asia-Pacific region [4].

V. E. Seliverstov examines the problems of the Russian Far East for which a new strategic course of development is announced. The author believes that the region's growing economy needs various metal products, necessitating organizational reforms, particularly construction of new metallurgical plants and development of a full-scale metallurgical industry in the region [5].

The authors' calculations [6] showed that because of regression between investments per capita from all sources and the economic growth rates of the regions of Eastern Russia, FDI and GRP growth show practically no correlation. I. P. Glazyrina et al. considered that new public policy instruments aimed to attract FDI did not significantly contribute to economic diversification of the Eastern regions during the period under review. In most areas, these investments were directed to the minerals sector. The authors believe that the problem of gradual transformation of institutions towards increasing their "inclusivity" is coming to the fore. Integration of investment policy and entrepreneurship support at the regional level can be significant if the Far Eastern development institutions are "reformatted" to solve this problem, providing the necessary resources [7].

N. V. Kashina compares the new concept of “priority development territories” for Russia with the existing constructions of “special economic zones” and “territorial development zones”, examines the characteristics of territories with a special tax regime, and the advantages for investors. The results obtained by the author confirm that residents of the newly created territories of advanced development in the Far East have more competitive and preferential business conditions compared to residents of special economic zones and territorial development zones in the Russian Federation [8].

A. A. Pankratov et al. quantified the TAD socio-economic potential of the Far Eastern Federal District. The authors considered the leading indicators of the Far Eastern Federal District TAD, determined their contribution to the dynamics of investments in fixed assets and employment of the population of the Far Eastern Federal District regions, identified groups of areas of the Far Eastern Federal District according to the degree of influence of TAD on the parameters of socio-economic and investment development [9].

A. G. Isaev considers the features of such instrument of spatial economic development policy as territories of advanced development (TAD). The author describes the formation of territories in the Far Eastern Federal District and their main distinguishing features from other types of territories with a special management regime. The fundamental possibility of using this policy tool to change the economic and technological structure of the Far East is indicated [10].

N. V. Lomakina analyzes the results of using state instruments to stimulate investment activity within the framework of the “new model” of development of the Russian Far East. The author shows the specifics of implementing instruments for localizing investments in a resource region (preferential regimes for priority development territories) and extraterritorial preferences in the form of direct subsidies from the federal budget for infrastructure facilities of investment projects and regional investment projects of strategic importance. According to the author, the results of implementing these tools in the Far Eastern Federal District in 2014-2020 show that a set of government measures to attract investment and its elements (tax benefits on mining, the criterion for maximizing private investment per ruble of the budget, etc.) stimulated the predominance of investments in mining in their total volume for all the support instruments under consideration [11].

Thus, the study of priority development territories allows analyzing the mechanisms of economic growth in regions with a low level of development. This, in turn, can help identify effective models and strategies that can be applied in the other areas of Russia and beyond.

Research on introducing new technologies and innovative solutions in priority development areas can contribute to developing scientific approaches to introducing innovations into the economy.

An analysis of the effectiveness of existing programs and initiatives for the development of the Far Eastern Federal District can help shape more effective government policies aimed at stimulating economic growth and improving living conditions in the District.

Thus, research into the TAD of the Far Eastern Federal District is scientifically significant both for understanding the specifics of regional development and for developing practical recommendations for improving the situation in these territories.

RESULTS

Russian agriculture, including in the Far East, has been subjected to serious challenges since 2014, such as restrictions on food imports from several countries, a sharp rise in prices, and increased cost of raw materials associated with the ruble's depreciation. The situation was further aggravated by the COVID-19 pandemic, which necessitated a ban on the entry of migrant workers. Thus, geopolitical and economic crises once again point to the instability of the Russian agricultural sector, which is critically dependent on a whole set of imported resources (including labor) [12, p. 330].

The Far Eastern Federal District is still more dependent than other federal districts on external food supplies from different regions of Russia and abroad [13; 14]. Only potatoes, corn, and soybeans are produced in sufficient quantities. The level of provision in the regions is insufficient for other products, especially meat. However, the situation in agriculture in the macroregion may improve due to attracting investors to projects in priority development areas [15].

TASEDarepart of the territory of a constituent entity of the Russian Federation, where, in accordance with the decision of the Russian Federation's government, a special legal regime was established for entrepreneurial and other activities to create favorable conditions for attracting investment, ensuring accelerated socio-economic development, and comfortable conditions for the population's livelihoods [16].

The first eight Priority Development Territories in the Far East were approved by the Government Commission for the Development of the Far East already in 2015 (Belogorsk TAD, Kamchatka TAD, Komsomolsk TAD, Mikhailovsky TAD, Nadezhdinskaya TAD, Priamurskaya TAD, Khabarovsk TAD, Chukotka TAD). Six more were added in 2016 (Bolshoy Kamen TAD, Amuro-Khinganskaya TAD, Gorny VozdukhTAD, Krasnokamensk TAD, Yuzhnaya TAD, South Yakutia TAD) , and five in 2017(TAD Selenginsk, TAD Svobodny, TAD Kuril, TAD Nakhodka (formerly Neftekhimicheskiy), TAD Nikolaevsk). In 2018, no new TAD appeared in the Far Eastern Federal District. In 2019, two TAD were formed (Buryatia TAD and Transbaikalia TAD). In 2020, two TAD were added to the macroregion (Yakutia TAD, Arctic Capital TAD)

[17, p. 578]. Since 2021, no new TAD have been formed in the Russian Far East; moreover, their number decreased due to the transformation of the Belogorsk, Priamurskaya, and Svobodny TAD operating in Amur Oblast into single Amur TAD (by Decree No. 3 of the Government of the Russian Federation dated January 10, 2023). This decision was made to improve the management system of priority development territories and increase the efficiency of efforts to create a favorable investment environment in Amur Oblast [18].

Thus, in 2023, the TASED were formed in all eleven subjects of the Federation as part of the Far Eastern Federal District. The leader is Primorsky Krai (four TAD); three are formed in Khabarovsk Krai and Sakhalin Oblast; the Trans-Baikal Territory, the Republic of Sakha (Yakutia) and the Republic of Buryatia have two TAD each; Kamchatka, the Chukotka Autonomous Okrug, the Jewish Autonomous Oblast, Murmansk and Amur Oblasts have one TAD each [19].

Creating TAD requires taking into account priority economic activities which are identified based on analyzing the development prospects of the Far East regions, which include: food and processing industry, as well as industrial construction (specialization of eight TAD), logistics (specialization of eight TAD), agriculture (specialization of six TAD), tourism (specialization of five TAD), mining (specialization of five TAD), fishing and fish processing (specialization of three TAD), wood processing (specialization of three TAD) and several others (see Table 1).

Table 1

Data on TAD specialization in the Far Eastern Federal District (2023)

Name	Specialization
Kamchatka	Tourism cluster, recreation, logistics, fishing, and fish processing
Komsomolsk	Mechanical engineering, wood processing, metalworking, and the food industry
Mikhailovsky	Agricultural industry
Nadezhdinskaya	Industry, logistics
Khabarovsk	Industry, logistics, agriculture
Chukotka	Mining, public services
Bolshoy Kamen	Shipbuilding, logistics
Amuro-Khinganskaya	Agriculture, food industry, logistics
Gorny Vozdukh	Tourist cluster, recreation
Krasnokamensk	Mining operations
Yuzhnaya	Agricultural industry

South Yakutia	Mining
Selenginsk	Tourism, recreation
Kuril Islands	Tourist cluster, fish processing
Nakhodka / Neftekhimicheskaya	Chemistry and petrochemistry
Nikolaevsk	Ship repair, fish processing, and mining
Buryatia	Agriculture, wood processing, and tourism cluster
Transbaikalia	Mining, wood processing, and the food industry
Yakutia	Agriculture, logistics, and the manufacturing industry
Capital of the Arctic	Port activities, logistics, and industrial construction
Amur	Logistics, industry

Compiled by the authors according to [20]

Sources reveal disagreement about assessing the effectiveness of creating and operating the TASED, and offer no single methodology. The scientific literature suggests the following indicators to evaluate TASED effectiveness: population consolidation, job creation, capital return (the ratio of industrial production to investment resources) [20, pp. 34-35], time interval for registration and commissioning, number of economic activities [21, p. 176], compliance with environmental requirements [22, p. 57], number of attracted residents and declared investments, ratio between public and private investments.

The Ministry of Regional Development of Russia proposes to fix the indicator of attracting at least three rubles of private funds per budget ruble among the criteria for TASED effectiveness. According to the calculations of the Corporation for the Development of the Far East and the Arctic specialists, one ruble of budget funds invested in creating infrastructure now accounts for 18.5 rubles of private investments.

Another indicator here is the added value that investors create per ruble of budget investments in infrastructure. Residents of such territories do not have benefits for value-added tax; therefore, when receiving added value at enterprises operating in the TASED, the budget will receive additional revenues.

Another indicator of effectiveness can be the federal budget's cost of creating one new workplace [23, p. 10]. On the official website of the Corporation for the Development of the Far East and the Arctic, indicators of the TAD development, such as the number of residents, investments in billions of rubles, and the number of jobs, are freely available (see Table 2).

Table 2

TAD development indicators in the Far Eastern Federal District in 2021-2023

	Residents,units			Investments,billionrubles			Jobs,units		
	2021	2022	2023	2021	2022	2023	2021	2022	2023
Kamchatka	116	121	126	174,50	123	124	11 305	12 550	12 955
Komsomolsk	23	26	26	38.90	159.82	179	4 019	6 328	6 174
Khabarovsk	42	54	58	28.40	39.82	38	3 043	3 493	3 664
Nikolaevsk	8	8	9	2.80	3	3	1 251	1 248	1 248
Chukotka	58	61	65	606.60	607	610	5 801	5 933	9 854
Bolshoy Kamen	24	25	28	393.90	398.68	529	17 182	17 669	24 751
Mikhailovsky	19	18	20	83.22	87.35	91	4 313	4 496	5 146
Nadezhdinskaya	77	87	97	60.70	65	66	8 017	8 589	8 686
Nakhodka / Neftekhimicheskaya	2	4	5	861.40	861.60	862	5 925	8 159	8 186
Amuro-Khinganskaya	4	3	3	7.60	5.29	8	1 163	556	466
Gorny Vozdukh	28	30	31	21.70	26	28	1 577	1 933	2 073
Yuzhnaya	10	10	14	17	17.10	18	1 171	1 282	1 397
Kuril Islands	7	8	8	11	11.81	12	1 903	1 998	2 017
Krasnokamensk	4	3	2	11.20	13.42	13	1 250	1 222	1 013
Transbaikalia	35	37	45	200.80	220	303	10 180	10 309	12 411
South Yakutia	18	19	19	111.10	113	113	8 861	10 727	10 738
Yakutia	29	35	41	12.90	14	15	1 591	2 094	2 212
Selenginsk	-	1	1	-	-	24	24		
Buryatia	13	12	14	12.60	8.14	8	1 723	953	1 000
Arctic	8	8	9	103.70	162	170	4 495	5 170	5 333
Belogorsk	6	6	-	5.40	5.39	-	921	882	-
Amur Region	20	22	-	10.70	11	-	1 323	1 395	-
Svobodnaya	9	11	-	1 789	1 791	-	4 157	4 761	-
Amur	-	-	40	-	-	1 852	-	-	7 050

Compiled by the authors according to [21]

Table 2 shows that a continuous positive growth trend in TAD in the Far Eastern Federal District in 2021-2023 is observed in Chukotka, Bolshoy Kamen, Nadezhdinskaya, Nakhodka (formerly Neftekhimicheskaya), Gorny Vozdukh, Yuzhnaya, the Kuril Islands, Transbaikalia, South Yakutia, Yakutia, and Capital of the Arctic. Of the three TAD that became part of Amurskaya TAD in January 2023, an increase in indicators was observed in Priamurskaya and Svobodnaya, while Belogorsk experienced a decrease. The leader in the number of residents is Kamchatka, in the number of investments – Amur, and the number of jobs – Bolshoy Kamen. The worst indicators are observed in the Amuro-Khinganskaya and Selenginsk.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Since the beginning of the TASED in the Far Eastern Federal District, the socio-economic indicators of the region have not improved significantly. According to most experts and the identified performance indicators, the positive dynamics of the education and activities of the TASED in the Far Eastern Federal District are either insignificant or absent [24; 25]. This is mainly due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the complex geopolitical situation, and mobilization of already limited labor resources in connection with the Special Military Operation in Ukraine. At the moment, the territories of advanced development are not fulfilling the tasks assigned to them. The macroregion is developing to a greater extent by using the advantages of natural resources (water, wood, energy, minerals).

At the same time, the TASED in the Russian Federation is a relatively new tool that will continue to transform and change depending on the tasks and needs of individual regions. The provided preferences are already beneficial – the current policy in the format of priority development territories has a positive effect on the business were created. In the future, it is possible to almost completely eliminate the shortage of food of local origin and significantly reduce the cost of food in the Far East. However, the search for investors, including foreign ones, is not to be stalled, as the potential of existing projects cannot significantly change the socio-economic situation in the Far Eastern Federal District.

The prospect of future research is to conduct more in-depth studies to evaluate the TASED long-term effectiveness. Based on the analysis, recommendations can be developed to improve the mechanisms of TASED functioning, which can contribute to more efficient use of budget funds and attract investments. Prospects include the possibility of integrating the TASED with neighboring regions to create larger economic clusters, which can enhance the overall competitiveness of the Far East. Exploring the possibilities of introducing innovative technologies and approaches (for example, digitalization and sustainable development) within the framework of TASED can open up new horizons for their development.

Thus, the topic opens up opportunities for further study and creation of effective strategies for developing TASED in the Far Eastern Federal District.

REFERENCES

1. Treivish, A. I., & Litvinenko, T. V. (2015). Eastern Russia: Space, role, and problems of development. *Regional Research of Russia*, 5, 203–211. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S2079970515030107>

2. Seliverstov, V. E. (2022). The “Five-Year Plan” of Spatial Development and Regional Policy of Russia: Running in Place or Readiness for a Sprint?. *Regional Research of Russia*, 12, 177–191. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S2079970522020228>
3. Dzhurka, N. G. (2018). Development Trajectories of the Russian Far East: Evaluation Based on the Dynamic Model of Economic Interactions. *Studies on Russian Economic Development*, 29, 144–152. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1075700718020028>
4. Minakir, P. A. (2017). The Far East and Transbaikalia on the eve of the reform: The concept of entering the market. *Prostranstvennaya ekonomika*, 1, 17–51.
5. Arkhipov, G. I. (2017). An overview of the state and priorities of the iron and steel industry in the Russian Far East. *Studies on Russian Economic Development*, 28, 271–277. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1075700717030030>
6. Glazyrina, I. P., Faleychik, L. M. & Faleychik, A. A. (2021). Institutional Policy and the Role of Foreign Direct Investment in the Far East of Russia. *Regional Research of Russia*, 11, 625–637. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S2079970521040043>
7. Glazyrina, I. P., Faleychik, L. M. & Faleychik, A. A. (2021). Institutional Policy and the Role of Foreign Direct Investment in the Far East of Russia. *Regional Research of Russia*, 11, 625–637. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S2079970521040043>
8. Kashina, N. V. (2016). Advanced development territories: A new tool for attracting investments to the Russian Far East. *Journal Economy of region*, 12 (2), 569–585.
9. Pankratov, A. A., Kuvshinova, E. A. & Galstyan, L. S. (2021). Quantitative Assessment of the Socioeconomic Potential of Advanced Development Territories of Regions of the Far Eastern Federal District. *Studies on Russian Economic Development*, 32, 407–414. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1075700721040110>
10. Isaev, A. G. (2017). Advanced development territories: A new instrument of regional economic policy. *EKO*, 4, 61–77.
11. Lomakina, N. V. (2021). State Incentivization of Investment Activity in a Resource Region: far Eastern Version. *Regional Research of Russia*, 11, 638–647. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S2079970521040110>
12. Zhupley, I. V., Potenk, T. A., & Schmidt, Yu. I. (2020). Threats to the agricultural sector of the Far Eastern Federal District of the Russian Federation: lessons from crises. *Economics and Entrepreneurship*, 119 (6), 330–334. (in Russ.)
13. Potenko, T. A. (2020). Agricultural policy and import substitution opportunities in the Russian Far East/T. A. Potenko, I. V. Zhupley, Y. I. Schmidt, L. P. Kvashko. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science: III International Scientific Conference: AGRITECH-III-2020: Agribusiness, Environmental Engineering and Biotechnologies, Volgograd, Krasnoyarsk*. Krasnoyarsk Science and Technology City Hall of the Russian

- Union of Scientific and Engineering Associations. Vol. 548. Volgograd, Krasnoyarsk, Institute of Physics and IOP Publishing Limited, 2020. P. 22011. DOI: 10.1088/1755-1315/548/2/022011
14. Zhupley, I. V. (2020). Challenges to agriculture in the Russian Far East: Lessons from crises / I. V. Zhupley, T. A. Potenko. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science, Khabarovsk*. Vol. 547. Khabarovsk, Institute of Physics Publishing, P. 012048. DOI: 10.1088/1755-1315/547/1/012048
 15. Turovsky, R. F. The Far East will provide itself with food. Information and analytical Internet resource East of Russia. Available at: <https://www.eastrussia.ru/material/vef-20/?ysclid=lel7y6uuzs1152925> (accessed on 12.02.2023) (in Russ.)
 16. Federal Law No. 473-FZ of December 29, 2014, "On Territories of Advanced Socio-Economic Development in the Russian Federation." Available at: <http://kremlin.ru/acts/bank/39279> (accessed January 10, 2023) (in Russ.)
 17. Obukhova, O. V., Proshko, N. F., & Kovalenko, S. V. (2021). Territories of advanced socio-economic development in the Far Eastern Federal District: assessment of preliminary results. *Economics and Entrepreneurship*, 137(12), 576–581. DOI: 10.34925/EIP.2021.137.12.110 (in Russ.)
 18. The government approved a resolution on the creation of a unified system for managing territories of advanced development in the Amur Region. Available at: <http://government.ru/docs/47516/> (accessed on 06.02.2023). (in Russ.)
 19. Territories of advanced socio-economic development. Official website. Far East and Arctic Development Corporation. Available at: <https://erdc.ru/about-tor> (accessed: 06.01.2023). (in Russ.)
 20. Egorov, N. A., & Postnikova, K. Yu. (2019). Features of the formation of ASEZs in the Far East. *International Research Journal*, 86 (8-2), 32–37. DOI: 10.23670/IRJ.2019.86.8.026 (in Russ.)
 21. Khabibrakhimov, A. Zh. (2018). TOSER: status granted – what next? *Bulletin of Kemerovo State University. Series: Political, Sociological, and Economic Sciences*, (3), 176–182. DOI: 10.21603/2500-3372-2018-3-176-182
 22. Mirzekhanova, Z. G. (2019). Advanced development territories in the Russian Far East: expectations and reality. *Regional Problems*, 22 (2), 55–61.
 23. Current issues of advanced socio-economic development of the Far Eastern macro-region. Information and analytical material. Analytical Department of the Federation Council Secretariat. URL: council.gov.ru (accessed: 10.01.2023).
 24. Torkunov, A. V., Streltsov, D. V., Koldunova, E. V. (2020). Russia's turn to the East: achievements, problems, and prospects. *Polis. Political Studies*, 29 (5), 8–21. DOI: 10.17976/jpps/2020.05.02.

25. Khabibrakhimov, A. Zh. (2018). TOSER: status granted – what next? *Bulletin of Kemerovo State University. Series: Political, Sociological, and Economic Sciences*, (3), 176–182. DOI: 10.21603/2500-3372-2018-3-176-182
26. Dukanich L. V., & Kuvshinova E. A. (2020). Multi-criteria Assessment of Entrepreneurial Activity in the Regions of the Far Eastern Federal District. *Scientific Research of Faculty of Economics*, 12(3), 7-15. (In Russ.). <https://doi.org/10.38050/2078-3809-2020-12-3-7-15>
27. Plyaskina, N. I., Kharitonova, V. N. & Vizhina, I. A. (2017). Policy of regional authorities in establishing petrochemical clusters of Eastern Siberia and the Far East. *Regional Research of Russia*, 7, 225–236. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S207997051703008X>
28. Seliverstov, V. E. (2018). Strategic Planning and Strategic Errors: Russian Realities and Trends. *Regional Research of Russia*, 8, 110–120. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S2079970518010082>
29. Adamaitis, S. A. (2021). The Role of Industrial and Technology Parks in the Socioeconomic Development of Russian Regions. *Regional Research of Russia*, 11, 648–655. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S207997052104002X>
30. Seliverstov, V. E., Melnikova, L. V., & Kolomak, E. A. et al. (2019). Spatial Development Strategy of Russia: Expectations and Realities. *Regional Research of Russia*, 9, 155–163. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S2079970519020114>

INFORMATION ABOUT THE AUTHORS

Olesya V. Obukhova (Russia, Ussuriysk) – Cand. Sci. (Politic.), Associate Professor. Primorsky State Agrarian and Technological University. E-mail: obuxova.olesya@mail.ru

Available: <https://statecounsellor.wordpress.com/2023/09/01/obukhova/>

Received: Mar 17, 2023 | **Accepted:** Jun 12, 2023 | **Published:** Sep 1, 2023

Editor: Gerardo Reyes Guzman, PhD in Economics. Universidad IEXE, MEXICO

Copyright: © 2023 Obuhova, O. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Competing interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.